

CONCEPTUAL INTEGRATION OF MYTHOLOGEME “TROJAN HORSE”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7698879>

Abstract. *The perception and interpretation of the mythologemes occurs in different way for each person according to the national world picture. The article shows a cognitive analysis of lexical features of mythologemes in the example of a “Trojan horse”, which makes it possible to assess the integration of mythologeme into new concepts connected with daily life.*

Keywords: *mythologeme, myth, cognitive integration, generic space, conceptual blending, the blend.*

INTRODUCTION

The ability of mankind to infer knowledge, draw conclusions, make assessments, and make judgments is the foundation for conceptual blending, often referred to as conceptual integration. In other words, Conceptual Blending is essential to human thought and imagination, both of which are essential to cognitive functions and creative aspects of human cognition. ‘Blending theory’ and ‘conceptual metaphor’ theories are strongly interconnected with each other (Fauconnier, 1994), (Lacoff, Turner, 1989). The creators of the Blending theory, G. Fauconnier and M. Turner, sought to explain the function of language in the formation of meaning, particularly its "creative character."

MAIN PART

Conceptual blending can be explained as follows: on the basis of shared elements, the conceptual structures of two unrelated mental spaces (input spaces) connected by a generic space are projected onto a new mental space (a blend), which produces a new emergent structure that distinguishes the blend from the inputs.

A foundation for the cognitive understanding of linguistic devices is provided by the mechanism of conceptual blending. It applies particularly well to cognitive processing of metaphorical meanings with intricate conceptual structures. The issue of this theory's language embodiment is one of the fundamental issues with Conceptual Blending Theory. To summarize, one of the key duties is to list the linguistic terms used during the conceptual blending process.

The works of G. Fauconnier and M. Turner (2002) contain several linguistic instances, but the taxonomy of linguistic units based on conceptual blending has not been established yet. Our findings have demonstrated that Conceptual Blending Theory can be used to explain a variety of linguistic phenomena, including neologisms, derivative and compound terms, word combinations, phraseological units and linguaculturemes.

Conceptual blending, integration network, emergence structure, two or more input spaces, generic space, and the blend are the fundamental concepts of conceptual blending theory.

This complex network known as conceptual blending involves four mental spaces: input 1, input 2, generic space and the blended space.

The source domain (input 1) and the target domain (input 2) are both involved in the blending process. In source domain we give the concept is being integrated.

Target domains include conceptual categories like emotions, morals, thought, human connections, time, etc. and have a tendency to be more abstract and devoid of physical qualities. Two domains—the source and target—are brought together and connected as the two input spaces throughout the blending process using a generic space.

The generic space provides abstract data that both input spaces share. Since it can offer a tangible foundation for analogy—a comparison of two domains based on similarities—between the source and the target, the generic space is significant. It identifies correspondences between conceptual domains and generalizes over what is shared by input spaces.

A variety of mental areas creates the structure known as the conceptual integration network, where cognitive blending takes place. The network has two or more input spaces that each include data from a different cognitive domain. A tool for simulating the potential emergence of meanings is an integration network.

Emergence structure is the creation of new meanings as a result of the fusion of the source and destination domains. It is the meaning which is bigger than the sum of its component components.

Specific structural elements from each of the input spaces are present in the blended space. The blended space borrows from both inputs while also conducting some alterations that add new, "innovative," meanings.

This means that the mix contains new information not included in any of the inputs.

Two input spaces interact and permeate each other based on a common (general) domain. This achieves partial equivalence between the two conceptual domains. However, this equivalence has certain characteristics. It contains completely new elements, sometimes inconsistent and incomplete elements. The main principle of conceptual fusion is therefore that the integration of structures yields more than the sum of its parts. New conceptual meanings emerge through the interaction of the two domain and destination thesauri, knowledge, experience, beliefs, cultural background, social status, etc.

The cognitive process known as conceptual integration or blending, according to Ashurova D. and Galieva M., forms the basis for the mechanism of mythologemes. This theory holds that the integration of structures that create more than the sum of their parts constitutes meaning construction. The uniqueness of mythologemes is a result of their intertextuality. The recipient and precedent texts' separate conceptual domains are combined into one on the premise of a mythologeme, evoking a number of associations and new conceptual senses.

Analysis of the conceptual integration of mythologeme “Trojan Horse”. In the 21st century mythologeme has another connotative meaning as the most powerful computer virus.

Sample Sentence: The email he sent to me contained a Trojan Horse virus that infected the computer.

The target domain “Trojan horse” as a mythologeme is interpreted here into the meaning of the source domain “Trojan horse” as a computer virus. So, there are two input spaces relating to the concepts “mythological trap”, “virus”. Both concepts deal with people’s invention which related to the object as “dangerous trap”. Trojan horse, the concept in the target space, according to the Greek Mythology during the Trojan War, the Trojans were held within their walls by the Greeks waiting outside. The Greeks left a gift—a giant wooden horse—outside the gates and then pretended to sail away. After the Trojans brought the horse into the city, the Greeks (hiding inside the horse) came out at night and conquered the city. Meanwhile, the term Trojan Horse that we can face in computing system is a program created to insult the security of a computer system while pretending to carry out some suspicious tasks. Both concepts presuppose the meaning any trick or scheme that prompts a target to allow an enemy inside a strongly guarded bastion or location has come to be known as a "Trojan horse." A "Trojan horse" or simply "Trojan" is a malicious computer software that deceive users into running it voluntarily. On the whole, it has a negative assessment/evaluation. A generic space represents four common notions like “defeats”, “trap”, “trick” and “weapon” are common to the both input spaces.

Elements from two input spaces above are mapped into the final result of integration and creates new meaning, in our case it is the blend. The blend generates new conceptual senses that the negative evaluation of both concepts are connected with a trap that can destroy enemies with using canny ways of war and this idea is expressed in both input spaces. So, the blend characterizing a secret trap that undermines and defeats enemies, provides an additional emergence structure conditioning that the features of the mythologeme a creation of Trojans to Romans is interpreted to the artificial creation of a mankind, computer programme in 21st century.

Conclusion

It should be emphasized once more in order to draw a conclusion that conceptual blending is a cognitive process that involves connecting unrelated ideas and creating new conceptual senses. Additionally, the theory of mental spaces and the theory of conceptual metaphors are linked to conceptual blending as a basic cognitive process. Conceptual blending includes two or more input spaces, a generic space, and a blend.

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